

Testing of Post-Fire Susceptibility to Brittle Cracking for X6CrNiTi18-10 Stainless Steel with Austenitic Structure

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ABSTRACT

The results of experimental research on the post-fire brittleness exhibited by the X6CrNiTi18-10 stainless, acid-resistant, chromium–nickel steel of austenitic structure are presented and discussed in detail. Formal reasoning is based on the results obtained in instrumented Charpy impact test. The samples have been cooled down after initial heat treatment simulating a priori fire action. Conditions of the test conformed to the steady-state heating regime. For comparison two fire scenarios have been considered, namely a fire of short duration with one-hour long heating period and a fire of long duration with heating period extended to ten hours. The samples have been heated in a muffle furnace with constant speed of 100°C/min until reaching one of two intentionally selected levels of temperature, i.e. 600°C or 800°C. First of these two levels, by assumption, was too low while the second was sufficiently high in order to induce in the samples examined a posteriori permanent changes in the microstructure, preserved in the tested material after cooling. Two qualitatively different cooling modes of the samples have been applied. In the first mode the samples have been cooled slowly in the muffle furnace to simulate self-extinguishing of the fire, while in the second mode the samples have been cooled rapidly, in water mist, to simulate the action of a fire brigade. The impact tests of cooled samples have been conducted at +20°C to model the expected behaviour of the tested steel during summer, and, for comparison, at –20°C to check the properties of the same steel grade when subjected to winter conditions.

Keywords: stainless steel, austenitic structure, post-fire brittleness, impact strength test.

1 INTRODUCTION – AUSTENITIC STAINLESS STEELS AND THEIR STRUCTURE AT FIRE TEMPERATURE

The X6CrNiTi18-10 stainless steel has been selected for detailed analysis as a material representative for acid resistant steels exhibiting austenitic structure. This is a high alloy chromium nickel steel with carbon stabilized by the addition of titanium. It is characterized by good weldability. It is also characterized by good resistance to corrosion, provided that the concentration of salts, chlorine, nitric and organic acids in its vicinity is low. It also serves well in all structures, where sufficient resistance to intercrystalline corrosion is sought after welding. Therefore it is usually used to make steel tanks and other structures of industrial construction. In the as delivered state this steel grade is usually oversaturated from the temperature of about 1100°C. It is also, within the group of special steels, representative for steels recommended for application at the temperature not exceeding 600°C (1). In the commercial nomenclature this steel grade is denoted as 1.4541 (Werkstoffnummer). Its properties are listed in detail in the code EN 10088-1 (2).

Our research was oriented on recognizing the susceptibility of the analyzed steel grade to brittle fracture, verified a posteriori, after surviving a fire episode simulated by heating program varying in duration and intensity, followed by effective cooling. We intended to find out the factors affecting post-fire brittleness of the tested steel, and as a consequence determine, which of these factors should

be considered decisive and which are of only secondary importance. Knowledge in this domain seems to be indispensable in drawing formal conclusions regarding the capability of the material tested here to safely resist the loads applied to it after surviving previous fire exposure.

It is widely known, that precipitation of deleterious secondary phases, and in particular sigma phase, initiated as a result of simulated fire exposure, presents particular risk in the typical stainless steel grades exhibiting austenitic structure. This usually occurs at the temperature range of 650–850°C.

Fig. 1. Structural changes in austenitic stainless steel typical for the 70% Fe-30% (Ni+Cr) ratio: a) equilibrium graph, b) TTT (Time – Temperature – Transformation) graph. One hour corresponds to 3600 seconds of sample heating.

It is clearly indicated in Fig. 1, that during the cooling process of the steel grade tested, uniform austenitic structure is created, containing separated chromium carbides (3). Precipitation of this type is unavoidable due to the limited carbon solubility in austenite. It is usually associated with the temperature of steel remaining within 450–900°C, but this phenomenon intensifies particularly at the temperature values around 700°C. Chemical composition of austenitic steels allows for development of a passive surface layer, resistant to action of concentrated oxidizing acids and their salts (4). Decreased chromium content in the carbides development zone often results in insufficient content of this element on grain boundaries, even below the steel passivation limit. This in turn may locally degrade its resistance to intercrystalline corrosion. Problems of this type are usually solved by addition of elements exhibiting strong carbide forming properties, such as for instance titanium and niobium, which bind to carbon more readily and permanently when compared against chromium.

It is usually assumed, that the deleterious secondary phases may precipitate in austenitic steels only when these steels are heated for a very long time at temperature ranging from 550°C to 900°C, lasting over 100 hours (5). Thus one may expect, that the potential fire exposure, affecting the steel for a much shorter time should not become an effective source of this type of precipitates.

2 TESTING SCENARIOS ASSUMED FOR ANALYSIS

An instrumented Charpy impact test has been assumed in our experiment as the primary tool to verify the post-fire susceptibility of X6CrNiTi18-10 steel grade to brittle fracture. Prior to testing, samples with V notch of shape prescribed by the code and standard dimensions (Fig. 2) have been cut out of 12 mm thick plate made of this steel. These samples have been subjected to preliminary

heat treatment of predetermined characteristics, simulating a fire action, and subsequently effectively cooled to ambient temperature. The tests followed the scenario of conventional steady-state heating regime, where a sample initially heated to predetermined temperature is subsequently kept at this temperature for a predetermined period of time.

Fig. 2. Details of the Charpy impact strength tests performed: at the left – shape and dimensions of samples used, at the right – instrumented hammer of the JB-W450E-L type.

Fig. 3. Fire simulation scenarios followed during the experiments: “short” fire – at the left, “long” fire – at the right.

Two alternative fire development scenarios have been considered, i.e. a “short” fire, where the steel had been heated for one hour, and a “long” fire with the heating time extended to ten hours (Fig. 3). Under both of these scenarios the samples have been initially heated to the predetermined temperature level at the speed of 100°C/min. The heating temperature values have been selected intentionally. In the first group of tests the heating temperature had been restricted to 600°C, while in the second group it had been raised to 800°C. These temperature levels are related to the typical allotropic transition temperature of “mild” carbon steels, i.e. transition of ferrite δ to austenite γ , occurring, at raising temperature in the $\delta \rightarrow \gamma$ direction, while at falling temperature in the opposite direction, i.e. $\gamma \rightarrow \delta$. A reference to these steels was forced upon us by the need to compare the obtained results with the results presented in, among others, papers (6-8). In our view, the first level of temperature was to be too low, while the second one was to be sufficiently high, to initiate and realize in practice with sufficiently high intensity permanent changes in the microstructure of the steel subjected to heating. These changes were expected to persist after effective material cooling.

After predetermined heating time the samples were effectively cooled. Two alternative cooling modes were applied, i.e. slow cooling of the samples in the cooling muffle furnace – this was intended

to simulate spontaneous and slow self-extinguishing of fire, and rapid cooling in water mist – corresponding to the typical firefighting action conducted by firefighters.

The impact strength tests have been conducted independently on two sets of samples cooled after a simulated fire exposure. These sets have been tested at +20°C – during the first series of tests and at –20°C during the second set of tests. The higher temperature of testing, according to the intent of the Authors, was to represent summer service conditions, while the second one was to simulate the winter conditions of service. In order to allow for proper statistical analysis of data obtained during the experiments, each case was independently tested on six separate samples. Finally 18 independent testing scenarios (two impact strength testing temperature values times two heating levels applied times two sample cooling modes times two simulated fire scenarios i.e. “short” fire or “long” fire, respectively plus two reference samples tested at +20°C and –20°C, respectively), resulted in $18 \times 6 = 108$ independently conducted tests. The reference samples, tested for comparison, have been made of the material in the as delivered state, meaning a material not subjected to prior heat treatment simulating a fire action. In order to properly identify obtained results a three character key has been used to indicate the treatment applied to each sample:

- first character, the digit 6 or 8 denotes the initial heating temperature level, i.e. 600°C or 800°C, respectively,
- second character, a letter S or L, denotes the fire scenario applied in practice, i.e. S – a “short” fire, or L – a “long” fire, respectively,
- third character, a letter F or W, indicates sample cooling mode applied during the test, i.e. F – slow (free) cooling inside muffle furnace or W – rapid cooling in water mist.

The reference samples, regardless of the impact strength testing temperature always have been identified with the digit 0.

3 THE FORCE – DISPLACEMENT RELATIONSHIP AS A DETERMINANT OF POST-FIRE RESISTANCE OF THE TESTED MATERIAL TO BRITTLE FRACTURE

Detailed conclusions regarding post-fire susceptibility of tested material to brittle fracture have been drawn based on the shape of experimentally obtained $F-s$ curve depicting the relationship between the force F [kN] breaking tested sample and the displacement of the force application point s [mm] measured in the direction perpendicular to the longitudinal axis of such sample (Fig. 4). Each $F-s$ curve has been obtained during an instrumented Charpy impact strength test. The force F_{gy} depicted on this graph is usually associated with initiation of plastic deformation in the developing impact fracture, while the force F_m , global maximum of the analyzed curve, with accompanying displacement determines the end of stable fracture initiation phase. With a further increase in displacement, the already initiated crack undergoes stable growth such that its propagation continues with plastic deformation. Initiation of unstable fracture growth phase occurs only at the displacement corresponding to the force F_{iu} . This phase ends when the displacement reaches the magnitude corresponding to the force F_a . At this moment an effective self-restriction of the fracture so far growing in an unstable manner begins, and as a consequence the sample enters the phase of finishing plastic fracture. Particular sample fracturing phases may be expressed by the components of fracturing energy $W \approx KV$ [J], usually presented in combination on a pie chart (Fig. 4).

According to the code ISO 14556 (9) shape of the $F-s$ curve obtained during the tests should be compared against one of the patterns denoted with subsequent letters of the alphabet, i.e. A, B, C, D, E and F (Fig. 5). Only an unstable, meaning brittle, fracture growth pattern is associated with the extreme pattern denoted as A. The second extreme pattern denoted as F is associated with the fracture growth pattern devoid of unstable growth phase. All the fracture growth phases are stable there, meaning that the fracture growth arrest is completely successful. The larger the area below the experimentally obtained $F-s$ curve, however determined for the displacement exceeding the one associated with the force F_a , the higher the capacity of the sample material to effectively arrest the unstable growth of previously initiated fracture. This in turn results in larger area of ductile finishing fracture observed on the severed surface.

Fig. 4. Sample fracturing phases identified on the $F-s$ curve, and fracture energy components determined based on that curve and presented as a pie chart.

Fig. 5. Location of standard $F-s$ curves on the $KV-T$ curve (description in the text).

The $F-s$ curve patterns depicted in the code have been assigned to individual locations, this time shown on the curve illustrating the relationship between the sample breaking energy (KV [J]) and the temperature of testing (T [$^{\circ}C$]). Conclusions regarding brittleness of steel drawn here are related to the limit fracturing energy $KV_{min}=27$ J, associated with ductile-to-brittle transition temperature (DBTT). The steels, for which at given temperature the experimentally determined fracturing energy had been lower than KV_{min} (i.e. those conforming to the patterns A, B, C and D), usually exhibit a dominating brittle character of the fracture. Therefore these steels are incapable of effectively self-arresting the developing brittle fractures and thus are not recommended for application in construction. The steels exhibiting such capability (i.e. those conforming to the patterns E and F) are characterized by the $F-s$ curves located at the right of threshold DBTT temperature.

4 INTERPRETATION OF THE OBTAINED RESULTS

The impact strength tests on samples made of X6CrNiTi18-10 steel have been conducted following the recommendations of the code (9) on instrumented Charpy hammer JB-W450E-L (Fig. 2), capable of delivering 450 J of potential energy. The hammer has been equipped with a transducer to measure the force applied to the sample, while the accompanying displacement of force application point was registered with an encoder. Signals generated by both transducers were gathered and processed by a data-logger with high sampling frequency and subsequently analyzed with specialized computer software. The results of each test have been registered on automatically generated graphs depicting force, energy and displacement as functions of time, or force and energy as functions of displacement. The same software automatically indicated the location of specific, characteristic limit points on these graphs as well.

Fig. 6. Results of the impact strength test conducted on the samples made of X6CrNiTi18-10 steel, subject to the following conditions: testing temperature +20°C, heating temperature 600°C, „short” fire samples cooled inside muffle furnace. Results averaged over a six element uniform statistical sample.

A typical result of the impact strength test executed following given testing scenario and averaged over six random realizations is depicted in Fig. 6. It is accompanied by graphs offset up and down by one empirical standard deviation (computed over statistical sample). The average values of particular limit points identified on the curve obtained are indicated as well, accompanied by the values of empirical standard deviation and coefficients of variation calculated for these points. The experimentally determined force – displacement graph ($F-s$) in each considered case has been supplemented with corresponding fracturing energy – displacement ($KV-s$) relation.

Figs 7-10 depict collective juxtaposition of $F-s$ curves obtained experimentally on samples made of X6CrNiTi18-10 steel after effective cooling preceded by simulated fire action following several development scenarios. On each of these figures graphs obtained on samples subjected to simulated fire are accompanied by the graphs obtained on samples preserved in the as delivered state, i.e. not affected by the action of fire temperature. The $F-s$ curves corresponding to the “short” fire scenario are compared against each other in Fig. 7, while these obtained following the “long” fire scenario are compared in Fig. 8. In both these juxtapositions the top figure refers to the impact strength tests conducted at +20°C, while the bottom figure refers to the tests conducted at -20°C, respectively. The juxtapositions depicted in Figs 9-10 are of different character, as they depict the permanent influence exerted by the cooling mode applied to the samples on their post-fire susceptibility to brittle fracture. The graphs presented in Fig. 9 refer to the impact strength tests conducted at +20°C, while those juxtaposed in Fig. 10 are related to the analogous tests conducted at -20°C. Regardless of the testing temperature, the top graph refers to the slow sample cooling mode inside the muffle furnace, while the bottom one refers to rapid cooling in water mist.

Should one assume that the area delimited from above by the $F-s$ curve represents the energy dissipated during fracture, and required to effectively break the sample, then one may notice that in the case of X6CrNiTi18-10 steel fire action usually results in permanent decrease of this energy post

fire, and therefore decreases the impact strength of the material tested with respect to the material tested in the as delivered state. This reduction proved to be significantly higher when the tests were conducted at lower temperature. As depicted in Fig. 5, the shape of $F-s$ curve obtained during the tests may be used to forecast the expected character of the fracture surface. When evaluating curves obtained during the tests conducted on material in the as delivered state, i.e. not affected by previous action of fire temperature and denoted on the graphs by the symbol 0, then in the cases conducted at $+20^{\circ}\text{C}$, they may unequivocally be assigned to the pattern F in the sense of the code (6) (Fig. 5). This means, that the forecast fracture would, under these circumstances be completely plastic, thus eliminating the risk of initiation and unrestrained propagation of brittle fractures in given steel when subjected to external loads. The shape of reference curves obtained during the tests conducted at the temperature -20°C proved to be somewhat different. In the Authors' opinion it still may be assigned to the pattern F , however it seems to be much closer to the pattern E (Fig. 5). This means, that under those conditions the probability of brittle fracture is undoubtedly higher, although still rather insignificant.

Fig. 7. Results of the impact strength test conducted on the samples made of X6CrNiTi18-10 steel following the “short” fire scenario, subject to various test conditions: the top figure – testing temperature $+20^{\circ}\text{C}$, the bottom figure – testing temperature -20°C . Results averaged over a six element uniform statistical sample.

As indicated above, the a’priori fire exposure of tested samples, preceding impact strength tests leads to permanent decrease in impact strength exhibited by the tested steel post fire. In the case of tests conducted at -20°C , the patterns of the $F-s$ relationships proved to be dangerously close to the pattern E , meaning that this grade of steel kept in service after surviving a fire episode may, in winter conditions, yield a certain risk of predominately brittle failure. Post-fire reduction of the impact

strength, verified here, proved to be significantly higher when the “long” fire scenario had been applied to the samples (Figs 9-10). Longer action of high temperature on the material resulted in intensified precipitation of deleterious compounds weakening its structure. During simulation of the “short” fire, due to the limited heating time these compounds did not have the chance to reveal themselves in full. In the case of a “short” fire, the higher temperature resulted in higher reduction of post-fire impact strength. The longer heating time applied when following the “long” fire scenario has to be associated with formally inverse statement (Figs 9-10). This result may be explained by the higher solubility dynamics of the secondary phase precipitates at higher temperature, in turn resulting in diminished harmful influence of this factor.

Fig. 8. Results of the impact strength test conducted on the samples made of X6CrNiTi18-10 steel following the “long” fire scenario, subject to various test conditions: the top figure – testing temperature +20°C, the bottom figure – testing temperature -20°C. Results averaged over a six element uniform statistical sample.

Verification of the post-fire impact strength dependence exhibited by the X6CrNiTi18-10 steel on the sample cooling mode applied in practice leads to the unequivocal statement, that in all the considered cases, regardless of the testing temperature higher reduction of this property has been achieved when the sample had been cooled in the muffle furnace. This means that in the case of this steel the possible hardening phenomenon at rapid cooling by water mist proved to be rather insignificant. Higher influence has to be attributed here to prolonged exposure of cooling steel to the action of high temperature, which in turn results in greater opportunity offered to the development of harmful precipitates.

Fig. 9. Averaged F - s curves obtained experimentally on samples made of X6CrNiTi18-10 during impact strength tests conducted at $+20^{\circ}\text{C}$ after application of: at the top – slow cooling in the muffle furnace, at the bottom – rapid cooling in water mist.

Fig. 10. Averaged F - s curves obtained experimentally on samples made of X6CrNiTi18-10 during impact strength tests conducted at -20°C after application of: at the top – slow cooling in the muffle furnace, at the bottom – rapid cooling in water mist.

5 CONCLUDING REMARKS

During the tests presented here we have strived to prove that the instrumented Charpy impact strength test may be applied as effective experimental tool to allow for drawing reliable conclusions regarding potential extended service of steel cooled after surviving a fire incident, as one has to decide whether such steel is capable of safely resisting the service loads applied to it. The key question here, in our opinion, is the post-fire capability exhibited by the tested material to resist the brittle fracture. This seemed to be poorly noticed and therefore very rarely verified in practice. The detailed results of these tests conducted on samples made of X6CrNiTi18-10 steel, exhibiting austenitic structure, proved to be non-trivial. The final conclusion drawn, of not only qualitative but more so quantitative character is affected by many factors. This is not only the fire episode scenario followed, but also the cooling mode applied after fire as well as the temperature and conditions at which the tested material is expected to serve in the future. In our opinion this type of differentiation is a visible result of permanent structural changes taking place in this material.

The results presented here, formulated based on the experimentally obtained $F-s$ curves had been formally confirmed during independently conducted fractographic and metallographic research. This is discussed in detail in papers (6-8).

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